

Introducing DALAM:

A Proposed UArctic Thematic Network

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What Is DALAM?

DALAM is the acronym for Decolonization of Arctic Library and Archives Metadata, a PLC-sponsored network of 23 individuals from 17 organizations in seven countries working together to create respectful and culturally appropriate subject headings, descriptive terminology, and metadata for Arctic collections related to Indigenous peoples.

What Are Our Goals?

- To help libraries and archives correct the culturally inappropriate, incorrect, and coloniality centered metadata, subject headings, and descriptive records which currently exist in Arctic collections.
- To support Indigenous peoples in defining the ways in which they and their environments are described in this domain.
- To make Arctic Indigenous languages more present in metadata, subject headings, and descriptive records.
- To build infrastructure, practices, tools, and relationships among Thematic Network partners to promote sustainability going forward.

Why a Thematic Network?

Many libraries and archives have inappropriate subject headings, metadata, and descriptions. We all have to solve this problem, so let's solve it together. If you are working in this area or are interested in decolonization, you are welcome to join us!

When Will This Happen?

The PLC's Thematic Network Proposal will be presented to the University of the Arctic Assembly in early June 2022.

Where Can I Learn More?

Contact Sandy Campbell at sandy.campbell@ualberta.ca.

Twenty Years Ago This Summer

20th PLC, 7–11 June 2004, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada

